

Sedimentary Texture Analysis for Optimal Siting of Managed Aquifer Recharge Basins, Northern and Eastern San Joaquin County, California

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Abstract This geologic analysis is being done in support of a Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) feasibility study for groundwater banking in northern and eastern San Joaquin County. Groundwater supply aquifers in the Great Basin of central California are generally in a state of overdraft, particularly in the San Joaquin River sub-basin, according to recent studies by the USGS. A conjunctive use supply strategy using surplus surface water flow to replenish aquifers using recharge basins is being tested by Stockton East Water District (SEWD), San Joaquin County, California. The hydrogeologic and engineering feasibility study being conducted is Phase I of the larger Water Supply Enhancement Project for the SEWD and is consistent with the aquifer replenishment goals of the Eastern San Joaquin Integrated Regional Water Management Plan. The objective of the MAR FS is to provide SEWD with information on the best locations for spreading basins within the 516-square-mile project domain to conduct artificial recharge operations. The percolation rate and penetration depth of recharge water from surface spreading basins are strongly controlled by the overall lithologic texture of underlying materials (e.g., interconnectedness of strata). A site-specific understanding of sedimentary texture is essential for the success of MAR. The unconsolidated sedimentary basins in the Central Valley of California are characterized by large variations in grain size distribution and sorting. As a result, grain-size distribution can change dramatically, both horizontally and vertically, depending on the location within a sub-basin. We modified (localized) a binary classification scheme originally developed by the US Geological Survey (Faunt, C.C. et al. 2009; Page, R.W. 1983 and 1986) to analyze 545 geologic logs obtained from the Department of Water Resources under the public authority rights of SEWD. Using the results of the binary lithologic texture classification, kriging geostatistics were performed to produce four-dimensional representations of lithologic continuity and texture distribution (spatial 3D plus color shade for textural grade) for the MAR FS domain to depths up to 1,000 feet. A variety of color-shaded maps were produced showing areas of percent coarse lithologic texture. Using GIS, the kriged geostatistical volume was combined with boundaries of the Public Land Survey System and modern land use base mapping for SEWD management use and further site-specific investigation. The study to date has identified good candidate locations to test different forms of MAR.

Keywords: conjunctive use, managed aquifer recharge, geologic texture analysis, recharge basin

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